

PRAGMALINGUISTIC ASPECTS OF COMPOUND NOUNS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6481797>

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Annotation: *This article discusses the compound nouns in English and Uzbek and their pragmalinguistic aspects. The pragmatic features of compound nouns can serve as a sign of a clearer understanding of their meaning in the text. Differences in the use of pragmatics in English and Uzbek, their specific features are analyzed.*

Key words: *linguistics, compound, pragmalinguistic, words, phrases, implication, proposition, intention.*

In world linguistics, the transition from the stage of studying language as a theoretical concept to practical linguistics began in the second half of the twentieth century. At this stage, the concept of language as a natural language differed from artificial language, and its specific features were analyzed in depth when applied in the context of a particular text. We know that in the process of speech not only linguistic units, i.e. words, phrases, compound words, fixed expressions and other compounds form active communication, but also extralinguistic factors such as personality, time and space factors, speech generator actions and facial expressions. Factors also have a direct impact on the speech process. Hence, it can be concluded that the study of semantic, grammatical and syntactic features of language alone is not sufficient. As a result, the field of "pragmatics" has found its place in linguistics, having its own goals and objectives. As S. Levinson describes: "Pragmatics is a field that studies the grammatical (coded) interactions between language and context in a linguistic structure, ... pragmatics is the study of all aspects of hidden meaning that semantic theory does not cover, ... analyzes the ability to select sentences appropriately to create context".

It is clear from these definitions that pragmatism has a wide scope; this field includes the analysis of concepts such as dexterity, communicative explication and implication, proposition, intention, presupposition, inference, speech act, discourse.

“Pragmatics” is derived from the Greek word *pragma* (*pragma*-action, action), which is actually a philosophical concept. It was also used in pre-Socratic times and was later adopted by philosophers such as J. Locke and E. Kant from Aristotle. Thus a stream of pragmatism emerged in philosophy. The main period of development of this movement is the XIX-XX centuries. Especially in the 20s and 30s of the twentieth century, the ideas of pragmatism began to be significantly promoted. The services of Ch. Pierce, R. Carnap, Ch. Morris, L. Wittgenstein in the widespread dissemination of this propaganda in America and Europe deserve special recognition.

In this article, we aim to evaluate and analyze the English compound nouns according to the types of attitudes expressed by the speaker in the communication process. This requires the study of linguistic phenomena that occur at the intersection of functional grammar and linguistic pragmatics, which are now beginning to develop widely. With this in mind, we will talk about how these terms of communicative grammar and linguistic pragmatics are used in modern linguistics, a brief history of their development and in what sense we use these terms in this dissertation research.

Traditional linguistics focuses on the study of linguistic units only from a formal point of view.

This view is further reinforced, especially by the semiotic approach to language, which assumes that the sign consists only of form. Each of the language levels was analyzed as a closed system. As a result, the relationship of linguistic units to the objective being represented by itself has been neglected. It later became clear that such a study of language was one-sided, that form could not be separated from meaning. As a result, attention is paid to the semantic side of linguistic units.

As a result of the intensification of semantic research in linguistics, it has become clear that even the description of linguistic units in terms of form and content does not allow a complete interpretation of language. Linguistic units can be properly understood only when they are studied in connection with the context, the situation of speech .

This increases interest in the pragmatic side of linguistic units. In order to understand the information correctly, in addition to the speakers' knowledge of language, it is necessary to add the listener's knowledge of the world, the

social situation in which the sentence is used, the speaker's psyche and other knowledge in the speech process.

The scientific views of the German philosopher G. Klaus, who studied pragmatics as a science that studied the relationship between characters and the creators, transmitters and receivers of these linguistic symbols, logically continue the ideas of Ch. Pierce and Ch. Morris in this field .

The views of J. May and D. Kim, linguists of the XXI century, on the field of linguopragmatics, its subject and its interaction with other fields are important. In particular, “Linguopragmatics (or pragmatics) is a branch of linguistics and semiotics that studies the cases and ways in which context influences meaning. Pragmatics includes the theory of speech act, the process of engaging in communication, interaction in conversation, and other features related to language in speech mode. In addition to linguistics and semiotics, this field is related to philosophy, sociology and anthropology

In conclusion, as a result of such a practical need, semantics and pragmatics emerged. Without these three aspects of linguistic units, language, which is a means of communication, cannot find its full interpretation.

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